

1. *SUBCULTURES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON
YOUTH*

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Abstract

Subculture (Latin: sub - "ost" and culture) is a term in sociology, anthropology, and cultural studies that refers to a sharply differentiated part of a society's culture. Within a subculture there may be specific clothing, slang, behavior and other cultural norms. Subcultures can be formed on national, demographic, professional, geographical and other grounds. In addition, subcultures among young people are distinguished separately. Under the influence of subculture, young people get attached to a stream and even go to the point of death. This is a tragic situation for the society and the young generation. The way they behave, dress, and perform various ceremonies cannot fail to influence other people, so it is necessary to direct the youth to religious and worldly knowledge. We must work together so that the spiritual consciousness is not shaped by the subculture.

Keywords: Subculture, Goth, Howard Becker, Jock Young, Gothic, Chicago School.

What is subculture? Early subculture theory included various theorists associated with what became known as the Chicago School. Subculture theory originated from the work of the Chicago School on gangs and developed through the School of Symbolic Interactionism into a set of theories that suggest that certain groups or subcultures in society have values and attitudes that promote

crime and violence. Work associated with the Center for Contemporary Cultural Studies at the University of Birmingham (CCCS) has been most responsible for linking the subculture to groups based on visual styles (teds, mods, punks, skins, bikers, etc.).

Acquiring status within a subculture required labeling and therefore exclusion from the rest of society, a group that treated outsiders with a certain hostility, so that non-compliance with dominant norms was often turned into a virtue. As the subculture became more meaningful, distinctive, and independent, its members became more and more dependent on each other for social contact and validation of their beliefs and lifestyles.

Howard Becker's themes of labeling "normal" society and subcultural dislike are also highlighted by, among other things, jazz musicians' emphasis on "fashionable" boundaries between themselves and their values and their audience as "squares". The notion of increased polarization between the subculture and the rest of society as a result of external labeling was further developed by Jock Young (1971) in relation to drug addicts in Britain, and in relation to moral panic in the media by mods and rockers Stan Cohen. According to Cohen, the generally negative portrayal of subcultures in the media reinforced dominant values and created the future shape of such groups.

Goth subculture (English: Goth subculture) is one of the modern subcultures and is spread all over the world. It started with the gothic rock scene in England in the 1980s. Unlike many other currents of that time, it has survived and diversified to this day. Goth clothing and lifestyle are influenced by 19th-century Gothic literature and horror films, and in some cases BDSM (bondage, discipline, sadism, masochism). Goths listen to gothic rock, deathrock, post-punk, darkwave, industrial, and neoclassical music. Goth subculture revolves around themes of depression, pessimism, and mourning. Black is the symbol of this culture. Goths' clothes are also dark night. It is difficult to distinguish them from each other, as men, along with women, wear their own make-up.

Goths" (translated from the English language "goths" - goths, that is, "barbarians", "uncivilized people", "ignorant") is a "subculture" that propagates vices such as immorality and inhumanity, which emerged in the 70s of the 20th century. appeared in Great Britain at the end of the 1990s. In particular, the opening of the music group "Betkav" in 1982 played a major role in promoting the goth lifestyle, and many similar groups began to spread it around the world. It was as a result of their work that the gothic-rock music genre was born and became popular not only among young English people, but also among young people all over the world.

The main idea behind the "Goth" movement is to promote death and the enjoyment of pain, suffering, and filth. In particular, they are characterized by an image based on black color, an interest in gothic music, living with the present and trying to get the most out of it, since it can be the last moment of life. Right now, instead of enjoying positive emotions, goths are enjoying mental anguish, despair. Goths also use unique symbols. Among them, the ankh with a cross-shaped appearance, the symbol of the human skull, crosses, straight and inverted pentagrams, and bats are the most common symbols. They also wear rings, pendants, pendants, satanic nodules, or death symbols.

They carry out the practice of wearing jewelry by piercing the tongue, lips, eyebrows and navel.

Goths love the fashion of the 18th and 19th centuries. Women long black skirts in combination with laces, gloves and long dresses or black tops, men's tailcoats and top hats. Another garment common to both sexes is the long black cloak.

As a result of such alienation in the spiritual culture of young people, they looking at all kinds of legends and myths as reality, they wanted the atmosphere in society they seek to adapt to social conditions. They are constant to the values they have created their culture contrary to the principles accepted by the public advance. However, every society has similar cultures compliance of specific, personal

creative initiatives and projects with the traditions of the state must pass through the filter. And this, in turn, is compliance with legal norms in state administration showing the importance of obeying the existing moral and legal freedoms in society will give. Working together as a team is proven effective in our country has results. Uzbeks believe that "the essence of our nation is collective no doubt. The collective people have their destiny, their goal, their national pride, to act in unison should be distinguished by strong motivation. Our nation is distinctly different from the French, Spanish or Russians by its collective nature, customs, traditions, and unique character stand". This alone is the national mentality of the youth of our country the fact that our ancestors are maturing with high spirituality, their continuity in the future clearly reflects. From the spiritual culture as a result of the activity of some young people in the subculture striving to limit formal values due to alienation, informal culture it manifests itself as a way of life, the meaning of social life. Therefore, subculture is an urgent problem among young people today. It suggested the formation of informal youth associations, their activities it is necessary to take a critical approach to the issues. Therefore, from the first years of independence in this regard, "Uzbekistan has also determined its development path. In this he refers to his history, carried out relation characteristic of the traditions and mentality of the population". That's it therefore, the spiritual culture of the youth in the society, the heritage of the ancestors scientific activities have been started in relation to this. Especially, in the last five years the role of important features, lifestyles and models in youth subculture carrying out a number of studies on identifying and studying changes in social behavior is going on

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